

Quantum-Chemical Study of the Relationships between Electronic Structure and the Affinity of Benzisothiazolylpiperazine Derivatives for the Dopamine Hd2l and Hd3 Receptors

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Abstract Schizophrenia is a mental illness that induces a cognitive deficit, affects a large part of the world's population, and in particular Africa where it is ignored. To treat this disease, the antipsychotic derivatives of benzisothiazolylpiperazine (N-(trans-4-(2-(4-(benzo [d] isothiazol-3-yl) piperazin-1-yl) ethyl)cyclohexyl) amides) are employed because of their inhibitory power for the dopamine HD2L and HD3 receptors. The present study aims to establish relationships between the electronic structure and the antipsychotic activity of benzisothiazolylpiperazine derivatives and to generate a 2D pharmacophore for predicting the antipsychotic activity of these derivatives. The KPG technique was employed. The electronic structure of all the molecules was calculated at the DFT/B3LYP/6-31G (d,p) level of theory. We obtained two statistically significant equations for predicting the inhibition constant. The process seems to be charge and orbital controlled for receptor HD2L and orbital controlled for HD3. The two prediction equations obtained can be useful for proposing new derivatives with antipsychotic activity having an affinity with the dopamine HD2L and HD3 receptors. The two pharmacophores derived from these prediction models would be very useful for proposing new molecules with potent antipsychotic activity.

Keywords Schizophrenia, QSAR, hD2L receptor, hD3 receptor, KPG method, DFT

Introduction

Schizophrenia is a serious illness that results in personality disorganization, disruption of family relationships, social isolation, and inability to work [1]. This disease, which begins in adolescence (15-25 years), is progressive and often irreversible, with a very high social cost, affecting 0.5 to 1% of the world population [2, 3].

Although schizophrenia is relatively rare, its early onset, its chronicity, its significant morbidity (one in four patients will attempt suicide), the inability of patients to work and the need for long hospital stays make this disease have a very high social cost [4]. This sickness due to the intrapsychic dissociation caused Neologism [5], and leads to primary signs (mental issues, discordance, atmosphere) and secondary signs resulting from the reaction of the patient's psyche (morbid rationalism, autism, paranoid delirium which is an attempt at psychic reconstruction) (Spaltung). There are different forms: simple, hebephrenic, hebephrenocatatonic, paranoid, schizo-neurotic, schizo-affective and heboidophrenia [6]. Considered as a spectrum disorder [7], schizophrenia is categorized by positive, negative, and cognitive symptoms. First-generation antipsychotics (FGAs), such as dopamine D2 receptor antagonists, effectively treat positive symptoms, but are ineffective in relieving negative symptoms or cognitive

disorders. FGAs can also cause serious side effects such as extrapyramidal symptoms (EPS) [8, 9]. In order to find remedies for symptoms or cognitive disorders, the synthesis of atypical antipsychotic derivatives of benzisothiazolylpiperazine for the treatment of schizophrenia is necessary because they affect the affinity for hD2L, hD3, 5-HT_{1A} and 5-HT_{2A} receptors individually and collectively as well [10].

In order to improve the antipsychotic activity of benzisothiazolylpiperazine derivatives for the treatment of schizophrenia and to determine the atomic sites most likely to interact in this activity, a QSAR study on these derivatives with the activity of inhibition on the dopaminergic hD2L and hD3 receptors was conducted.

Methods, Models and Calculations

Model

Consider the state of thermodynamic equilibrium between a drug and a following receptor:

Where $D_i R$ is the drug-receptor complex, R is the receptor D_i is the drug. The

equilibrium constant K_i for this reaction is defined as :

$$K_i = \frac{Q_{D_i R}}{Q_{D_i} Q_R} \exp(-\Delta \varepsilon_0^i / kT) \quad (2)$$

Where $Q_{D_i R}$, Q_{D_i} and Q_R are respectively the total partition functions of the drug-receptor complex, the drug and the receptor, and k and T respectively represent the Boltzmann constant and the absolute temperature. $\Delta \varepsilon_0^i$ is the difference between the ground-state energy of $D_i R$ and the energies of the ground-states of D_i and R .

After several physically-based approximations the following equations was obtained [11]:

$$\begin{aligned} \log(\text{ki}) = & a + bM_{D_i} + c \log \left[\sigma_{D_i} / (ABC)^{1/2} \right] + \sum_j \left[e_j Q_j + f_j S_j^E + s_j S_j^N \right] + \quad (3) \\ & \sum_j \sum_m \left[h_j(m) F_j(m) + x_j(m) S_j^E(m) \right] + \sum_j \sum_{m'} \left[r_j(m') F_j(m') + t_j(m') S_j^N(m') \right] \\ & + \sum_j \left[g_j \mu_j + k_j \eta_j + o_j \omega_j + z_j \zeta_j + w_j Q_j^{\max} \right] \end{aligned}$$

where a , b , c , e_j , f_j , s_j , $h_j(m)$, $x_j(m)$, $r_j(m')$, $t_j(m')$, g_j , k_j , o_j , z_j and w_j are constants, M_{D_i} is the drug's mass, σ_{D_i} is its symmetry number, ABC is the product of the drug's moments of inertia about the three principal axes of rotation, Q_j is the net charge of atom j , S_j^E and S_j^N are, respectively, the total atomic electrophilic and nucleophilic superdelocalizabilities of atom j , $F_j(m)$, $F_j(m')$ is the electron population (Fukui index) of the occupied (vacant) MO $m(m')$ localized on atom j , $S_j^E(m)$ is the atomic electrophilic superdelocalizability of MO m localized on atom j , μ_j is the local atomic electronic chemical potential of atom j , η_j is the local atomic hardness of atom j , ω_j is the local atomic electrophilicity of atom j , ζ_j is the local atomic softness of atom j , Q_j^{\max} is the maximum amount of electronic charge that atom j may accept from another site, and O_k is the orientational parameters of the k -th substituent.

It should be noted that the local atomic reactivity indices in equation 3 come from Hatree-Fock-Roothaan (HFR) framework [11, 12] and are defined as:

- The nucleophilic superdelocalizability of the local lowest empty MO (LUMO*) localized on atom i :

$$S_i^N(LUMO)^* = \frac{F_i(LUMO)^*}{E_{LUMO}^*} \quad (4)$$

This is a measure of the electron-accepting capacity of the local LUMO* of atom i.

- The local electrophilic superdelocalizability the highest occupied MO (HOMO*) localized on atom i:

$$S_i^E(HOMO)^* = \frac{F_i(HOMO)^*}{E_{HOMO}^*} \quad (5)$$

This is a measure of the electron-donating capacity of the local HOMO* of atom i.

- The local atomic hardness is defined as follows:

$$\eta_i = \left(E_{LUMO_i^*} - E_{HOMO_i^*} \right) \quad (6)$$

This index measures the resistance of atom i to exchange electrons with a site.

- The local atomic softness of atom i is defined as:

$$\zeta_i = 1/\eta_i \quad (7)$$

This index measures the facility of atom i to exchange electrons with the site.

- The local atomic electronic chemical potential is defined as follows:

$$\mu_i = (1/2) \left(E_{HOMO_i^*} - E_{LUMO_i^*} \right) \quad (8)$$

This index represents the measure of the propensity of atom i to gain or lose electrons.

- The maximal amount of which charge atom i may receive is defined as:

$$Q_i^{*max} = -\frac{\mu_i}{\eta_i} \quad (9)$$

- Local atomic electrophilicity of atom i is defined as:

$$\omega_i^* = \frac{(\mu_i)^2}{2\eta_i} \quad (10)$$

This index measures the propensity of atom i to receive extra electronic charge together with its resistance to exchange charge with a site.

Methods

The methodology used here to find relationships between the electronic structure and the inhibition constants has been discussed in several papers [12–19]. The results presented here are obtained from what is now a routine procedure. For this reason, this paper contains standard phrases for the presentation of the methods, calculations and results because they do not need to be rewritten repeatedly and the number of possible variations to use is finite [12–19]. The application of this method has led to outstanding results for a wide variety of drug system diversity (see [20–34] and related references).

Selection of molecules

The selected molecules are from a set reported in reference [10]. Their general formulas and biological activities are shown in Figure (1) and Table 1. The experimental data used are the inhibition constants, which is the affinity of the benisothiazolylopipezazine derivatives for the dopaminergic hD2L and hD3 receptors.

Figure 1: General formula of benzisothiazolypiperazine derivatives

Table 1: Selected of Benzisothiazolypiperazine derivatives used with their inhibition constants on hd2L and hd3

No.	Molecules	X	hD _{2L}	hD ₃
1	3-(trans-4-(2-(4-(Benzo[d]isothiazol-3-yl)piperazin-1-yl)ethyl)cyclohexyl)-1,1-dimethylurea	(CH ₃) ₂ N-	-0.28	-0.40
2	3-(trans-4-(2-(4-(Benzo[d]isothiazol-3-yl)piperazin-1-yl)ethyl)cyclohexyl)-1,1-diisopropylurea	(iPr) ₂ N-	-0.14	0.15
3	3-(trans-4-(2-(4-(Benzo[d]isothiazol-3-yl)piperazin-1-yl)ethyl)cyclohexyl)-1-ethyl-1-methylurea	(Et)(Me)N-	-0.29	-0.11
4	N-(trans-4-(2-(4-(benzo[d]isothiazol-3-yl)piperazin-1-yl)ethyl)cyclohexyl)morpholine-4-carboxamide		0.34	0.20
5	1-(trans-4-(2-(4-(benzo[d]isothiazol-3-yl)piperazin-1-yl)ethyl)cyclohexyl)-3-benzylurea		0.15	-0.74
6	1-(trans-4-(2-(4-(benzo[d]isothiazol-3-yl)piperazin-1-yl)ethyl)cyclohexyl)-3-phenylurea		-0.20	-1.37
7	1-(trans-4-(2-(4-(benzo[d]isothiazol-3-yl)piperazin-1-yl)ethyl)cyclohexyl)-3-(pyridin-3-yl)urea		-0.29	-1.26
8	3-(trans-4-(2-(4-(benzo[d]isothiazol-3-yl)piperazin-1-yl)ethyl)cyclohexyl)-1-methyl-1-phenylurea		0.38	0.08
9	Ethyl (trans-4-(2-(4-(benzo[d]isothiazol-3-yl)piperazin-1-yl)ethyl)cyclohexyl)carbamate	CH ₃ -CH ₂ -O-	-0.15	-1.24
10	N-(trans-4-(2-(4-(benzo[d]isothiazol-3-yl)piperazin-1-yl)ethyl)cyclohexyl)-2-methoxyacetamide	CH ₃ -O-CH ₂ -	0.98	-0.51
11	E. N-(trans-4-(2-(4-(benzo[d]isothiazol-3-yl)piperazin-1-yl)ethyl)cyclohexyl)acetamide	CH ₃ -	1.40	-0.80
12	N-(trans-4-(2-(4-(benzo[d]isothiazol-3-yl)piperazin-1-yl)ethyl)cyclohexyl)propionamide	CH ₃ -CH ₂ -	1.26	-1.28
13	N-(trans-4-(2-(4-(benzo[d]isothiazol-3-yl)piperazin-1-yl)ethyl)cyclohexyl)butyramide	CH ₃ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -	0.45	-0.85
14	N-(trans-4-(2-(4-(benzo[d]isothiazol-3-yl)piperazin-1-yl)ethyl)cyclohexyl)-2,2,2-trifluoroacetamide	CF ₃ -	0.23	-0.57
15	N-(trans-4-(2-(4-(benzo[d]isothiazol-3-yl)piperazin-1-yl)ethyl)cyclohexyl)cyclohexanecarboxamide		-0.03	-0.72

16	N-(trans-4-(2-(4-(benzo[d]isothiazol-3-yl)piperazin-1-yl) ethyl)cyclohexyl)cyclopropanecarboxamide		-0.07	-0.68
17	N-(trans-4-(2-(4-(benzo[d]isothiazol-3-yl)piperazin-1-yl) ethyl)cyclohexyl)benzamide		-0.48	-1.33
18	N-(trans-4-(2-(4-(benzo[d]isothiazol-3-yl)piperazin-1-yl)ethyl)cyclohexyl)furan-2-carboxamide		0.46	-0.89
19	N-(trans-4-(2-(4-(benzo[d]isothiazol-3-yl)piperazin-1-yl) ethyl)cyclohexyl)thiophene-2-carboxamide		-0.72	-1.25
20	N-(trans-4-(2-(4-(benzo[d]isothiazol-3-yl)piperazin-1-yl)ethyl)cyclohexyl)-1H-pyrrole-2-carboxamide		-0.68	-0.51
21	N-(trans-4-(2-(4-(benzo[d]isothiazol-3-yl)piperazin-1-yl) ethyl)cyclohexyl)nicotinamide		-0.07	-1.05
22	N-(trans-4-(2-(4-(benzo[d]isothiazol-3-yl)piperazin-1-yl)ethyl)cyclohexyl)-1H-indole-2-carboxamide		-0.37	-1.54

Calculations

The electronic structure of all molecules was calculated with density functional theory (DFT) at the B3LYP/6-31G (d, p) level with full optimization of the geometry. The Gaussian Program was used [35]. The D-Cent-QSAR software [36, 37] was used to compute the numerical values of local atomic reactivity indices from the Gaussian results. The software Statistica [38] was used for multiple linear regression analysis (LMRA). We also used the common skeleton hypothesis. The entire work process is explained in several documents (see references [20–34]). The skeleton common to all twenty-two antipsychotic molecules bearing the numbers of these different atoms is shown below:

Figure 2: Common skeleton of benzoisothiazolylpiperazine derivatives

Results

Results for the hD2L dopamine receptor

The best equation for the antipsychotic activity obtained for the dopaminergic hD2L receptor is as follows:

$$\log(ki) = 6.68 + 25.57F_{20} + 19.66Q_{24} + 45.83F_{17} (LUMO)^* - 0.78F_{26} (LUMO)^* - 0.48S_{18}^E (HOMO - 2)^* + 4.05F_{12} (HOMO - 2)^* + 0.45F_{25} (LUMO)^* \quad (11)$$

with $n = 21$, $R = 97.64\%$, $R^2 = 95.33\%$, $\text{adj-}R^2 = 92.82\%$, $F(7,13) = 37.91$, ($p\text{-value} = 1.17986E-07$) and $SD = 0.13$. No outliers were detected and no residuals fall outside the ± 2 limits.

This equation from the multiple linear regression shows that the antipsychotic activity of benzisothiazolylpiperazine derivatives (N- (4- (benzo [d] isothiazol-3-yl) piperazin-1-yl) ethyl) cyclohexyl amides) is related to seven local index of atomic reactivity: ζ_{20} is the local atomic softness of atom 20, Q_{24} is the net charge of the atoms 24, 25 and 26 $F_{17}(LUMO)^*$ is the Fukui index (electronic population) of the lowest vacant molecular orbital localized on atom 17, $F_{26}(LUMO)^*$ is the Fukui index of the lowest vacant molecular orbital localized on atom 26, $S_{18}^E(HOMO-2)^*$ is the electrophilic superdelocalizability of the third highest occupied molecular orbital localized on atom 18, $F_{12}(HOMO-2)^*$ is the Fukui index of the third lowest vacant molecular orbital localized on atom 12 and $F_{25}(LUMO)^*$ is the Fukui index of the lowest vacant molecular orbital localized on atom 25.

Tables 2 and 3 show the beta coefficients, the results of the t-test for significance of variable and the matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables of Eq. 11. There are no significant internal correlations between independent variables (Table 3). Figure 3 displays the plot of observed vs. calculated hd2L affinities.

Table 2: The statistical parameters of the template index for the hd2L receptor variables

Variables	Beta coefficients	P-value
ζ_{20}	0.546	6.00E-06
Q_{24}	0.747	0.00E+00
$F_{17}(LUMO)^*$	0.634	7.00E-06
$F_{26}(LUMO)^*$	-0.570	1.06E-04
$S_{18}^E(HOMO-2)^*$	-0.322	4.36E-04
$F_{12}(HOMO-2)^*$	0.288	1.80E-03
$F_{25}(LUMO)^*$	0.241	4.11E-03

Table 3: Squared correlation coefficients for the variables appearing in Eq. 11

Variables	ζ_{20}	Q_{24}	$F_{17}(LUMO)^*$	$F_{26}(LUMO)^*$	$S_{18}^E(HOMO-2)^*$	$F_{12}(HOMO-2)^*$
Q_{24}	0.005	1				
$F_{17}(LUMO)^*$	0.20	0.06	1			
$F_{26}(LUMO)^*$	0.18	0.36	0.45	1		
$S_{18}^E(HOMO-2)^*$	0.07	0.004	0.0004	0.01	1	
$F_{12}(HOMO-2)^*$	0.01	0.102	0.12	0.18	0.11	1
$F_{25}(LUMO)^*$	0.014	0.02	0.26	0.14	0.002	0.12

Figure 3: Plot of predicted vs. observed $\log(k_i)$ values from Eq. 1. Dashed lines denote the 95% confidence interval

Results for the hD3 dopamine receptor

The best equation for the antipsychotic activity obtained for the dopaminergic hD3 receptor is as follows:

$$\log(k_i) = 1.24 + 0.99\mu_{26} + 1.98F_{18}(HOMO-1)^* + 6.91S_{13}^N(LUMO+1)^* + 2.34S_{16}^N(LUMO)^* - 12.46F_1(HOMO)^* + 0.01S_{21}^N(LUMO)^* - 1.29S_{17}^N(LUMO)^* - 0.09S_{24}^E(HOMO)^* \quad (12)$$

with $n = 22$, $R = 97.53\%$, $R^2 = 95.11\%$, $\text{adj-}R^2 = 92.10\%$, $F(7,13) = 31.62$, ($p\text{-value} = 2.67184E-07$) and $SD = 0.14$. No outliers were detected and no residuals fall outside the ± 2 limits.

The equation resulting from the multiple linear regression shows that the antipsychotic activity of the benzisothiazolylpiperine derivatives depends on eight local atomic reactivity indexes: on the one hand; positive numerical values of the local atomic reactivity indexes. μ_{26} is the local atomic chemical potential of the atom 26, $F_{18}(HOMO-1)^*$ is the electronic population (Fukui index) of the second highest occupied molecular orbital localized on atom 18, $S_{13}^N(LUMO+1)^*$ is the nucleophilic superdelocalizability of the second vacant molecular orbital localized on atom 13, $S_{16}^N(LUMO)^*$ is the nucleophilic superdelocalizability of the lowest vacant molecular orbital localized on atom 16, $F_1(HOMO)^*$ is the Fukui index of the highest occupied molecular orbital localized on atom 1, $S_{21}^N(LUMO)^*$ is the nucleophilic superdelocalizability of the lowest vacant molecular orbital localized on atom 21, $S_{17}^N(LUMO)^*$ is the nucleophilic superdelocalizability of the lowest vacant molecular orbital localized on atom 17 and $S_{24}^E(HOMO)^*$ is the electrophilic superdelocalizability of the highest occupied molecular orbital localized on atom 24.

Tables 4 and 5 show the beta coefficients, the results of the t-test for significance of variable and the matrix of squared correlation coefficients for the variables of Eq. 12. There are no significant internal correlations between independent variables (Table 5). Figure 4 displays the plot of observed vs. calculated hD3 affinities.

Table 4: The statistical parameters of the template indexes for the hD3 receptor

Variables	Coefficients β	P-value
μ_{26}	1.026	0.00E+00
$F_{18}(HOMO-1)^*$	0.480	7.00E-06
$S_{13}^N(LUMO+1)^*$	0.657	4.00E-06
$S_{16}^N(LUMO)^*$	0.613	2.00E-06
$F_1(HOMO)^*$	-0.344	7.22E-04
$S_{21}^N(LUMO)^*$	0.267	1.12E-03
$S_{17}^N(LUMO)^*$	-0.269	5.81E-03
$S_{24}^E(HOMO)^*$	-0.184	2.93E-02

Table 5: Squared correlation coefficients for the variables appearing in Eq. 12

Variables	μ_{26}	$F_{18}(HOMO-1)^*$	$S_{13}^N(LUMO+1)^*$	$S_{16}^N(LUMO)^*$	$F_1(HOMO)^*$	$S_{21}^N(LUMO)^*$	$S_{17}^N(LUMO)^*$
$F_{18}(HOMO-1)^*$	0.06	1					
$S_{13}^N(LUMO+1)^*$	0.29	0.006	1				
$S_{16}^N(LUMO)^*$	0.06	0.01	0.06	1			
$F_1(HOMO)^*$	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.12	1		
$S_{21}^N(LUMO)^*$	0.002	0.02	0.0004	0.01	0.01	1	
$S_{17}^N(LUMO)^*$	0.08	0.04	0.002	0.27	0.24	0.02	1
$S_{24}^E(HOMO)^*$	0.02	0.008	0.11	0.06	0.16	0.04	0.14

Local Molecular Orbitals

Table 6: Local Molecular Orbitals of atoms 1, 12, 13 and 16

Molecules	Atom 1 (C)	Atom 12 (C)	Atom 13 (N)	Atom 16 (C)
1 (112)	106π107π112π- 113π114π116π	99σ111σ112σ- 117σ122σ123σ	106σ111σ112σ- 123σ127σ128σ	103σ104σ111σ- 119σ121σ123σ
2 (128)	122π124π128π- 129π130π133π	120σ127σ128σ- 140σ143σ145σ	120σ127σ128σ- 139σ143σ148σ	119σ120σ127σ- 136σ137σ138σ
3 (116)	111π112π116π- 117π118π121π	108σ112σ115σ- 121σ124σ128σ	105σ106σ115σ- 126σ134σ137σ	107σ108σ115σ- 122σ123σ125σ
4 (124)	117π119π123π- 124π125π127π	109σ115σ122σ- 133σ135σ137σ	117σ122σ123σ- 133σ135σ139σ	113σ114σ122σ- 134σ142σ143σ
5 (128)	124π127π128π- 129π130π135π	124σ127σ128σ- 135σ141σ144σ	124σ127σ128σ- 142σ147σ148σ	117σ118σ127σ- 136σ137σ142σ
6 (124)	117π119π123π- 125π126π130π	115σ119σ122- 130σ135σ138σ	112σ113σ122σ- 136σ140σ141σ	111σ112σ122σ- 131σ132σ133σ
7 (124)	120π123π124π- 125π127π131π	120σ123σ124σ- 134σ137σ138σ	120σ123σ124σ- 137σ138σ143σ	113σ114σ123σ- 133σ134σ136σ
8 (128)	123π127π128π- 129π130π135π	114σ115σ127σ- 139σ141σ143σ	116σ127σ128σ- 146σ149σ151σ	116σ117σ127σ- 138σ139σ141σ
9 (112)	108π110π112π- 113π114π117π	102σ104σ111σ- 122σ123σ125σ	108σ111σ112σ- 122σ123σ128σ	103σ104σ111σ- 122σ124σ125σ
10 (112)	107π109π112π- 113π114π117π	109σ111σ112σ- 125σ127σ128σ	103σ104σ111σ- 120σ123σ125σ	103σ104σ111σ- 119σ121σ124σ
11 (104)	99π100π104π- 105π106π109π	100σ103σ104σ- 116σ118σ119σ	96σ97σ103σ- 112σ114σ118σ	96σ97σ103σ- 111σ113σ115σ
12 (108)	103π104π108π- 109π110π113π	97σ107σ108σ- 113σ117σ120σ	103σ107σ108σ- 119σ120σ124σ	99σ101σ107σ- 117σ121σ122σ
13 (112)	107π108π112π- 113π114π117π	108σ111σ112σ- 124σ126σ127σ	104σ105σ111σ- 123σ128σ129σ	104σ105σ111σ- 118σ120σ121σ
14 (116)	113π114π116π- 117π118π121π	109σ114σ115σ- 121σ126σ127σ	107σ108σ115σ- 126σ129σ133σ	108σ109σ115σ- 122σ124σ127σ
15 (123)	118π119π123π- 124π125π128π	111σ114σ122σ- 128σ135σ138σ	111σ112σ122σ- 138σ140σ141σ	112σ113σ122σ- 130σ133σ135σ
16 (111)	106π107π111π- 112π113π116π	103σ107σ110σ- 116σ123σ124σ	100σ101σ110σ- 117σ121σ124σ	101σ103σ110σ- 118σ120σ121σ
17 (120)	115π116π120π- 121π123π126π	106σ107σ119σ- 131σ133σ136σ	115σ119σ120σ- 132σ133σ136σ	110σ111σ119σ- 134σ136σ138σ
18 (117)	112π116π117π- 118π120π123π	111σ116σ117σ- 126σ128σ130σ	112σ116σ117σ- 133σ136σ137σ	111σ116σ117σ- 125σ130σ132σ
19 (121)	115π117π121π- 123π124π128π	107σ108σ120σ- 135σ139σ142σ	115σ120σ121σ- 138σ139σ141σ	111σ112σ120σ- 129σ133σ137σ
20 (117)	113π116π117π- 118π120π122π	104σ116σ117σ- 129σ130σ131σ	107σ116σ117σ- 127σ133σ136σ	105σ107σ116σ- 126σ129σ131σ
21 (120)	115π117π120π- 122π124π127π	110σ119σ120σ- 127σ134σ138σ	115σ119σ120σ- 131σ134σ136σ	108σ109σ119σ- 128σ130σ133σ
22 (130)	124π126π130π- 132π133π137π	115σ116σ128σ- 141σ143σ145σ	128σ129σ130σ- 141σ143σ148σ	119σ120σ128σ- 142σ150σ151σ

Table 7: Local Molecular Orbitals of atoms 17, 18, 20 and 21

Molecules	Atom 17 (C)	Atom 18 (C)	Atom 20 (C)	Atom 21 (C)
1 (112)	103σ104σ111σ- 122σ125σ128σ	102σ103σ104σ- 123σ124σ125σ	108σ109σ110σ- 121σ123σ126σ	108σ109σ110σ- 118σ125σ129σ
2 (128)	119σ120σ127σ- 135σ151σ152σ	118σ119σ120σ- 141σ142σ143σ	123σ125σ126σ- 134σ135σ137σ	123σ125σ126σ- 132σ139σ142σ
3 (116)	106σ107σ115σ- 123σ124σ126σ	105σ106σ107σ- 127σ128σ129σ	110σ113σ114σ- 120σ125σ128σ	110σ113σ114σ- 120σ124σ125σ
4 (124)	113σ114σ122σ- 133σ138σ141σ	113σ114σ115σ- 135σ138σ139σ	118σ120σ121σ- 128σ138σ142σ	118σ120σ121σ- 128σ132σ133σ
5 (128)	117σ118σ127σ- 141σ142σ149σ	116σ117σ127σ- 136σ139σ141σ	117σ125σ126σ- 142σ144σ146σ	123σ125σ126σ- 134σ136σ139σ
6 (124)	112σ113σ122σ- 133σ136σ140σ	113σ114σ122σ- 135σ136σ140σ	113σ114σ120σ- 132σ143σ144σ	118σ120σ121σ- 133σ140σ142σ
7 (124)	114σ123σ124σ- 137σ141σ142σ	112σ113σ114σ- 135σ136σ137σ	112σ113σ118σ- 135σ139σ142σ	117σ118σ121σ- 130σ133σ135σ
8 (128)	117σ127σ128σ- 140σ141σ142σ	116σ117σ127σ- 138σ141σ145σ	116σ117σ125σ- 134σ138σ147σ	119σ121σ125σ- 131σ134σ136σ
9 (112)	103σ104σ111σ- 119σ121σ125σ	104σ105σ111σ- 121σ123σ124σ	105σ107σ109σ- 118σ121σ129σ	105σ107σ109σ- 116σ118σ122σ
10 (112)	103σ104σ111σ- 120σ121σ128σ	102σ103σ104σ- 121σ123σ126σ	106σ108σ110σ- 116σ118σ120σ	103σ108σ110σ- 116σ118σ120σ
11 (104)	96σ97σ103σ- 112σ113σ114σ	95σ96σ97σ- 113σ115σ118σ	97σ101σ102σ- 108σ112σ121σ	97σ101σ102σ- 108σ110σ112σ
12 (108)	99π101σ107σ- 117σ118σ121σ	99σ100σ101σ- 120σ122σ123σ	101σ105σ106σ- 112σ117σ123σ	101σ105σ106σ- 112σ114σ117σ
13 (112)	104σ105σ111σ- 118σ119σ121σ	103σ104σ105σ- 119σ121σ123σ	104σ109σ110σ- 118σ122σ123σ	104σ109σ110σ- 116σ123σ124σ
14 (116)	107σ108σ115σ- 122σ125σ128σ	106σ107σ108σ- 124σ125σ126σ	107σ108σ112σ- 122σ129σ130σ	108σ111σ112σ- 122σ123σ128σ
15 (123)	112σ113σ122σ- 129σ130σ131σ	111σ112σ113σ- 130σ134σ135σ	113σ120σ121σ- 132σ133σ136σ	113σ120σ121σ- 127σ131σ133σ
16 (111)	101σ103σ110σ- 117σ120σ124σ	101σ103σ109σ- 119σ122σ123σ	100σ101σ109σ- 122σ125σ126σ	105σ108σ109σ- 115σ121σ122σ
17 (120)	110σ111σ119σ- 133σ137σ138σ	109σ110σ111σ- 133σ136σ138σ	114σ117σ118σ- 138σ143σ145σ	111σ117σ118σ- 127σ128σ129σ
18 (117)	108σ116σ117σ- 125σ134σ135σ	106σ107σ108σ- 126σ128σ130σ	107σ108σ114σ- 124σ129σ130σ	113σ114σ115σ- 129σ130σ133σ
19 (121)	111σ112σ120σ- 131σ132σ135σ	112σ118σ120σ- 135σ139σ140σ	116σ118σ119σ- 129σ131σ133σ	116σ118σ119σ- 127σ130σ134σ
20 (117)	107σ116σ117σ- 125σ126σ127σ	106σ107σ116σ- 125σ132σ133σ	106σ107σ114σ- 128σ132σ133σ	110σ112σ114σ- 125σ133σ134σ
21 (120)	108σ109σ119σ- 128σ131σ138σ	108σ109σ119σ- 132σ136σ137σ	109σ116σ118σ- 126σ130σ132σ	113σ116σ118σ- 126σ130σ131σ
22 (130)	119σ120σ128σ- 141σ143σ149σ	118σ119σ120σ- 143σ148σ149σ	120σ123σ125σ- 139σ149σ150σ	120σ123σ125σ- 139σ140σ141σ

Table 8: Local Molecular Orbitals of atoms 24, 25 and 26

Molecules	Atom 24 (N)	Atom 25 (H)	Atom 26 (C)
1 (112)	108σ109σ110σ- 118σ119σ127σ	94σ95σ108σ- 116σ117σ118σ	108σ109σ110π- 117π118σ119σ
2 (128)	123σ125σ126σ- 132σ134σ135σ	98σ108σ123σ- 132σ134σ136σ	123π125σ126π- 132σ134π136σ
3 (116)	110σ113σ114σ- 120σ122σ135σ	99σ102σ110σ- 120σ123σ124σ	110σ113π114σ- 120π122σ124σ
4 (124)	118σ120σ121σ- 128σ129σ136σ	88σ102σ118σ- 127σ128σ129σ	118σ120σ121π- 127σ128π129σ
5 (128)	123σ125σ126σ- 134σ145σ149σ	96σ97σ114σ- 136σ137σ138σ	123σ125σ126σ- 131σ134π136π
6 (124)	120σ121σ124σ- 127σ128σ133σ	97σ98σ118σ- 131σ132σ133σ	118π120σ124σ- 127σ128π131σ
7 (124)	118σ121σ122σ- 128σ132σ133σ	82σ89σ95σ- 130σ131σ132σ	118σ121σ122σ- 126π128σ130π
8 (128)	124σ125σ126σ- 131σ134σ147σ	103σ104σ121σ- 136σ138σ139σ	121π125π126σ- 131π132σ134π
9 (112)	107σ109σ110σ- 116σ118σ121σ	87σ88σ107σ- 116σ117σ118σ	105π107σ109σ- 116π117σ118π
10 (112)	106σ108σ110σ- 116σ120σ130σ	64σ87σ106σ- 116σ118σ120σ	106π108σ110π- 116π118π120σ
11 (104)	96σ101σ102σ- 108σ112σ120σ	81σ83σ102σ- 110σ112σ113σ	96σ101σ102σ- 108σ110π114π
12 (108)	101σ105σ106σ- 112σ135σ144σ	89σ99σ106σ- 114σ115σ117σ	101π105σ106σ- 112π114π118π
13 (112)	103σ109σ110σ- 116σ119σ135σ	96σ109σ110σ- 118σ119σ120σ	103π109π110π- 116σ118π122π
14 (116)	108σ111σ112σ- 119σ123σ128σ	91σ96σ111σ- 122σ123σ125σ	101σ111σ112σ- 119σ122π131π
15 (123)	113σ120σ121σ- 127σ130σ131σ	89σ105σ121σ- 131σ132σ133σ	113π120σ121σ- 127σ130π131π
16 (111)	105σ108σ109σ- 115σ119σ125σ	90σ91σ108σ- 117σ118σ119σ	105π108σ109σ- 115π117π126π
17 (120)	114σ117σ118σ- 122σ127σ128σ	88σ96σ100σ- 124σ126σ127σ	114π117π118σ- 122π127π128σ
18 (117)	113σ114σ115σ- 119σ122σ125σ	95σ99σ113σ- 124σ125σ126σ	113σ114π115σ- 119σ122π125π
19 (121)	116σ118σ119σ- 122σ127σ131σ	92σ98σ116σ- 125σ130σ133σ	108π116π118σ- 122σ127π130π
20 (117)	112σ114σ115σ- 119σ124σ134σ	85σ92σσ95σ- 122123125	110π112π114π- 119σ122π124σ
21 (120)	114σ116σ118σ- 121σ123σ126σ	86σ88σ92σ- 123σ126σ128σ	114π116π118σ- 121σ123π126π
22 (130)	125σ127σ129σ- 131σ135σ136σ	99σ106σ123σ- 137σ138σ139σ	116π123π125π- 131π135π136σ

• The local molecular orbital of molecule 19 and 22

Atom 26 is a carbon atom of the amide function of the common skeleton is a molecular orbital of nature π and σ . The figure below shows this orbital in the molecule 19:

Figure 5: Molecular orbitals of molecule 19

The orbital in the molecule 22 shows that these orbitals are π -nature for atom 1.

Figure 6: Molecular orbitals of molecule 22

Discussion

Discussion of the hD2L dopamine receptor results

The statistical parameters show that:

The probability of Fischer $F(7,13) = 37.9 > F(7,13)_{\text{tabbed}} = 2.83$ which implies that the equation is significant at the level $\alpha(0.5)$. Thus, there is only a 5% probability that there is no real link between antipsychotic activity and local reactivity index.

The p-value or probability value $p = 1.17986E-07 < 5\%$ percent so the regression equation is statistically significant. The antipsychotic activity is strongly correlated to 97.64% of the local atomic index obtained in the model.

Observing the values of the beta coefficients (Table 2), we can classify the variables by the following priority order:

$$Q_{24} > F_{17}(LUMO)^* > F_{26}(LUMO)^* > \zeta_{20} > S_{18}^E(HOMO-2)^* > F_{12}(HOMO-2)^* > F_{25}(LUMO)^*$$

The p-values of the index are greater than 0.001; these indexes are not statistically significant at 0.1%. Next the analysis will be done with the other variables.

As the inhibition constant K_i is a measure of the interaction force between the drug candidate and the target. The lower value of K_i correspond to the stronger interactions of benzisothiazolyloperazine derivatives with the receptor. Thus, the analysis variable per variable suggests that a good antipsychotic activity of the benzisothiazolyloperazine derivatives is linked to low numerical values for the indexes ζ_{20} , $F_{17}(LUMO)^*$ for those indexes are positive as well as their coefficients, with a low negative value of $S_{18}^E(HOMO-2)^*$ because the coefficient is negative and at a high positive value of $F_{26}(LUMO)^*$ because the coefficient is negative and a high negative value of Q_{24} .

Atom 20 is a carbon atom of cyclohexane. A low numerical value of ζ_{20} implies a large value of the HOMO-LUMO gap including a resistance of this atom to electron transfer with other fragments. Then the atom should be substituted by an electron deficient center.

Atom 24 is a nitrogen atom bound to cyclohexane. It is normal that its net charge Q_{24} is negative; a large negative value of this index suggests that the atom 24 interacts with an electropositive center of the D2 receptor; this interaction could be done through the lone pair of the nitrogen atom.

Atom 17 is a carbon atom bound to cyclohexane. A low value of $F_{17}(LUMO)^*$ implies that the atom 17 is substituted by an electron deficient center. This interaction shall be from type σ - σ (See table 7).

Atom 26 is a carbon atom of a carbonyl group. A large value $F_{26}(LUMO)^*$ indicates that the atom 26 interacts with an electron-rich (substituent) center. Moreover, all the molecular orbitals located on this atom are generally σ and π type (See Table 8). So this interaction will be σ or π type.

Atom 18 is a carbon atom of cyclohexane. A low negative value of $S_{18}^E(HOMO-2)^*$ corresponds to a weak donor character of the atom 18. The appearance of (HOMO-1) in the activity implies that the molecular orbitals (HOMO)* and (HOMO-1)* also participate in the biological activity. In addition, the orbital located on this atom

are all from type σ . Thus the molecular orbitals (HOMO)*, (HOMO - 1)* of the atom 18 interact with a center rich in electrons but these interactions are σ type (See Table 7).

All these suggestions are presented on the partial 2D-pharmacophore of fig 5.

Figure 7: 2D pharmacophore for the affinity of benzisothiazolylpiperazine derivatives with h2L dopaminergic receptor

Discussion of the hD3 dopamine receptor results

The statistical parameters show that:

$F(8,13) = 31.62 > F(8,13)_{\text{tabbed}} = 2.77$ so the global template is statistically significant with risk $\alpha = 0.05$. This means that there is only a 5% chance that there is no real link between antipsychotic activity and local reactivity indexes.

$P = 2.67184E-07 < 0.05$ implies that the multiple linear regression equation is statistically significant. $R = 97.53\%$ shows that there is a strong correlation between the local atomic reactivity indexes and the conducted biological activity.

The values analysis of coefficients beta (Table 4) makes it possible to classify the variables following the priority order:

$$\mu_{26} > S_{13}^N(LUMO+1)^* > S_{16}^N(LUMO)^* > F_{18}(HOMO-1)^* > F_1(HOMO)^* > S_{17}^N(LUMO)^* > S_{21}^N(LUMO)^* > S_{24}^E(HOMO)^*$$

The variables $S_{21}^N(LUMO)^*$, $S_{17}^N(LUMO)^*$ and $S_{24}^E(HOMO)^*$ will not be considered during the analysis variable per variable since they are not significant at 0.1% because their P-value are all greater than 0.1%.

As the inhibition constant K_i is a measure of the interaction force between the drug candidate and the target. Thus, the analysis variable per variable suggests good antipsychotic activity of benzisothiazolylpiperazine derivatives is associated with low numerical values of $F_{18}(HOMO-1)^*$, $S_{13}^N(LUMO+1)^*$ and $S_{16}^N(LUMO)^*$, large negative value of μ_{26} and high positive value of $F_1(HOMO)^*$.

Atom 26 is a carbon atom of a carbonyl group. A large negative value of μ_{26} suggests that the LUMO and the HOMO must be lowered on the energy axis. So, therefore, this atom must interact with an electron rich center such as for instance a carboxylate group.

Atom 18 is a carbon atom of cyclohexane. The appearance of (HOMO-1)* implies that (HOMO)* also participates in antipsychotic activity and thus, a low positive value of $F_{18}(HOMO-1)^*$ implies orbitals (HOMO-1)* and (HOMO)* of the C18 atom interact with an electron rich center but this is about an interaction σ - σ (table 7).

Atom 13 is a nitrogen atom. A weak numerical value of negative of $S_{13}^N(LUMO+1)^*$ returns to a low electro acceptor capacity. The presence of (LUMO + 1)* leads us to say that (LUMO + 1)* and (LUMO)* participate in the biological activity. Thus, the molecular orbitals (LUMO + 1)* and (LUMO)* of the N¹³ atom interact with a poor center of the dopaminergic hD3 receptor, but these interactions are of the type σ - σ (Table 6).

Atom 16 is a carbon atom. A low and negative numerical value of $S_{16}^N(LUMO)^*$ corresponds to a low electro acceptor capacity. Then the orbital (LUMO)* of this atom must interact with a center that is poor in electrons. According to table 6, this interaction is from type σ - σ .

Atom 1 is a carbon atom. A high numerical value of $F_1(HOMO)^*$ suggests that for a good biological activity, the orbital (HOMO)* of the atom 1 interacts with a poor center in electrons. Moreover, all the molecular orbitals of this atom are π type (See table 6). So this interaction is from type π - π .

All these suggestions are presented on the partial 2D-pharmacophore of fig 8.

Figure 8: 2D pharmacophore for the affinity of benzisothiazolylpiperazine derivatives with hD3 dopaminergic receptor

Conclusions

These pharmacophores were obtained with statistically significant results concerning the variation of the numerical values of a definite set of local indices of atomic reactivity and the variation of the antipsychotic activity of the benzisothiazolylpiperazine derivatives to improve the activity of the latter. The results should be useful to propose new molecules that have higher antipsychotic effects for the treatment of schizophrenia. The pharmacophores proposed show that the actions of the benzisothiazolylpiperazine derivatives on the hD2L and hD3 receptors have different mechanisms.

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